

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF POLYPROPYLENE/FUNCTIONALIZED GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES

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1. General Introduction

Conductive polymer composite materials deserve interest in several application fields [1]. A composite consisting of conductive fillers and an insulating polymer becomes electrically conductive as the filler content exceeds a certain critical value, which is generally attributed to percolation phenomenon. These percolation threshold values for the particular polymer composites can be drastically reduced by using nano-sized conductive fillers such as carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers etc. Recently, two dimensional structures based on carbon such as graphene has received significant attention owing to their astonishing electronic, thermal and mechanical properties [3-5]. Owing to a high aspect ratio, outstanding electrical conductivity and cost efficiency, graphene can act as effective conductive filler in polymer as compared to carbon nanotubes. Till date several researches have been carried out based on graphene/polymer composites using graphene as nanofiller [6-10]. In the present report, we have attempted to functionalize the graphene by introducing amine groups and studied its influence on the properties of the polypropylene nanocomposites.

2 Experimental

2.1 Synthesis of octadecylamine grafted graphene (G-ODA)

Graphene oxide (GO) was synthesized through modified hummer's method [11]. The synthesized GO was subjected to thionyl chloride treatment at 70° C for 24 hrs to convert the surface bound carboxylic groups into acyl chloride groups. The mixture of the resulting solid (1 g) and octadecylamine (ODA) (5 g) was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere at 80° C for 96 h. After cooling

to room temperature, the resulting solid mixture was placed in a soxhlet extractor and ethanol was employed as extraction solvent to remove the excess amine. After 24 h, the ethanol solution was discarded and chloroform was used as extraction to obtain the amine functionalized graphene. The product was dried at 50° C in vacuum overnight before use.

2.2 Preparation of polypropylene/functionalized graphene nanocomposites:

Polypropylene composites based on graphene oxide and functionalized graphene oxide are prepared through melt blending with various loading levels ranging from 0.1 to 5 wt % using bradender plasticorder set at the speed of 50 rpm and the mixing was continued for 5 min. In all set experiments, maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene was used as the compatibilizer. It was then dumped and pressed at 200 °C for 2 min using a Carver press to prepare 0.15 mm thick sheet.

2.3 Characterization studies

Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopic characterization (FT-IR) of graphene filler and polypropylene nanocomposites was carried out using Perkin-Elmer (FT-IR) spectrophotometer. X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies of filler as well as polypropylene composites were done using Bruker X-ray diffractometer. Surface characteristics of the graphene fillers were determined using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, PHI 5700, PHI com). Morphological characterization of graphene and its composites were carried out using Transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Jeol JSM-2010) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Stereoscan 440). Tensile properties of the polymer composites were determined using Instron tensile

tester set at the stretching rate of 5 mm/min. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) measurements studies of both graphene fillers and its composites were performed on Perkin-Elmer Pyris 1 under a nitrogen atmosphere from room temperature to 600°C. Differential scanning calorimetric studies (DSC) of graphene and its nanocomposites were done using Perkin-Elmer differential scanning calorimeter.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Synthesis of octadecylamine grafted graphene

The obtained ODA grafted graphene samples are black powder. In the present investigation, the reaction between the GO and octadecylamine has been carried out at various intervals of time viz. 12, 24 48 and 96 h. Structural characterization using FT-IR reveals the successful grafting of ODA onto the graphene surface. Fig. 1 shows the FT-IR results of GO, GO-COCl and GO-ODA.

Fig. 1 FT-IR results of graphene oxide samples

The peak corresponds to the -C=O stretching of -COOH group at 1712 cm^{-1} shift to higher wave number (1734 cm^{-1}) corroborating the conversion of -COOH to -COCl on thionyl chloride treatment of GO. Appearance of strong peaks at 2922 and 2850 cm^{-1} that corresponds to -CH asymmetric and symmetric stretching of -CH_2 groups in ODA confirms its successful grafting on GO surface. The peak corresponds to -OH stretching (3442 cm^{-1}) in GO shifts to higher wave number (3470 cm^{-1}) with significant decrease in peak intensity reveals the formation of -CONH linkages on the GO surface on

treatment with ODA. This is further corroborated by the appearance of broad band in the range of 1615 to 1480 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to C-N stretching and NH bending vibrations of -CONH groups present on the GO-ODA surface. DSC results revealed that the melting peak of ODA grafted onto graphene is relatively broader compared to the pure ODA corroborating the successful grafting of ODA on the graphene surface. The chemical grafting of ODA on the surface of graphene is further corroborated using XPS. Appearance of peak at 399 eV that corresponds to N1s reveals the grafting of ODA on GO surface (Figures not shown). X-ray diffraction studies of GO and GO-ODA are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 XRD results of graphene oxide samples

In case of GO, the peak corresponding to (002) plane ($2\theta = 26^\circ$) of graphite completely vanishes with the appearance of new peak at around $2\theta = 12^\circ$, which corresponds to (001) plane. The average d-spacing between the graphene planes in GO is observed to be 0.73 nm . There is no variation in the peak position corresponding to (001) in GO-ODA revealing the fact that there is no significant variation in crystal structure of GO due to ODA grafting. The average d-spacing between the graphene planes in GO-ODA is observed to be 0.72 nm .

The morphological characterization of the GO and GO-ODA are done using TEM and the results are displayed in Fig. 3 (a-b). Graphene nanosheets are observed to form a covering on the

top of the copper grid, like transparent silk. Graphene nanosheets are scrolled and entangled with each other (Fig. 3a). Corrugation and scrolling are part of the intrinsic nature of graphene nanosheets, which results from the fact that the 2D membrane structure becomes thermodynamically stable via bending. Similar results observed in case of GO-ODA system consisting of several stacked layers of graphene platelets (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 3a: TEM result of GO

Fig. 3b: TEM result of GO-ODA

The successful grafting of ODA on the graphene surface is further corroborated based on TGA results. Fig. 4 shows the TGA results of GO-ODA sample. GO-ODA undergoes maximum degradation in the temperature range of 300 to 480° C with the maximum weight loss of about 32 wt % at 650° C. GO is not thermally stable and weight loss started below 100° C with

rapid loss at 150° C. The weight loss at lower temperature for GO is attributed to the higher defect density present in it due to the introduction of labile oxygen containing groups such as -OH, -COOH groups [12]. However grafting of ODA significantly reduces the defect density and thereby improves the thermal stability relative to GO [12].

Fig. 4: TGA result of GO-ODA

3.2 Preparation and characterization of polypropylene nanocomposites based on functionalized graphene

Polypropylene composites based on GO and G-ODA are carried out through melt blending technique. In all set of experiments, about 10 wt % of MA-g-PP is used as compatibilizer. Mechanical properties such as tensile strength and elongation at break of the compression molded polypropylene composites are determined for polypropylene composites based on GO and G-ODA. Tensile strength of the ODA grafted Graphene exhibits significantly higher value compared to the GO, which may be attributed to the increased polymer-filler interaction. For instance, on loading 1 wt % of GO in PP composites compatibilized with maleic anhydride grafted PP, tensile strength is observed to be 32.5 ± 2.4 MPa, which is significantly raised to 47.1 ± 1.0 MPa on loading 1 wt % of GO-ODA. This improvement in tensile property is attributed to the chemical interaction between maleic anhydride present in the compatibilizer and the -NH groups present on the graphene surface that ultimately results in higher

polymer-filler interaction. Tensile strength and elongation at break (EB) values of PP composites increases with GO-ODA content as depicted in Fig. 5 and 6. Significant improvement in tensile property is attributed to the increase in polymer-filler interaction with increase in GO-ODA content. The improvement in EB values with GO-ODA content is corroborated to the plasticizing effect of long hydrocarbon chain present in ODA.

Fig. 5 Variation of tensile strength with varying GO-ODA content in PP composites

Fig. 6 Variation of elongation at break with varying GO-ODA content in PP composites

Fig. 7 shows the variation of electrical resistance with GO-ODA content in PP composites. As expected the electrical resistance decreases with increasing GO-ODA content with the electrical percolation limit at 0.63 wt % of GO-ODA.

Fig. 7 Variation of electrical resistance with GO-ODA content in PP composites.

Summary:

Polypropylene composites based on GO and ODA functionalized GO were prepared through melt blending technique using maleic anhydride grafted PP as compatibilizer. Initially, GO prepared through modified Hummer's method was functionalized with ODA and successful grafting of ODA on the GO surface was confirmed through using various characterization tools. PP composites based on GO-ODA showed significant improvement in mechanical and electrical properties due to the enhanced dispersion of GO-ODA in the PP matrix.

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